

Analysis of the production system of a corrugated board company

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Abstract

This project was developed within the framework of Project-Based Learning (PBL), with an emphasis on solving real-world problems and improving the performance of industrial processes. Carried out at a cardboard company (SMSA), in collaboration with the company's Continuous Improvement manager, the project's main focus was on improving the operational efficiency of the entire industrial process. The main objective was to identify bottlenecks in the flow and increase its capacity. Through an in-depth assessment of several processes in various sections, we identified the palletising and packaging unit as the main bottleneck. The inconsistent time recording data provided by the company posed a significant challenge in the analysis. To overcome these obstacles, we had to collect data in the field and carried out simulations of different operational scenarios to evaluate potential improvements and propose data-based solutions. This project emphasises the role of systematic analysis in enhancing industrial processes, demonstrating how a structured, data-driven approach can generate measurable operational benefits. By increasing the efficiency and capacity of the palletising and packaging unit, our results not only contribute to better operational performance at SMSA but also illustrate the practical applications of the PBL methodology in solving complex industrial challenges.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning (PBL), Corrugated Cardboard Industry, Bottleneck, Production System

1 Introduction

The Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology has been widely applied in Engineering and Industrial Management education, fostering active learning by challenging students to solve real-world problems in authentic organizational contexts. At the University of Minho, PBL has been implemented successfully for over a decade, leading to significant development of both technical and transversal skills, including teamwork, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Barros et al., 2017; Lima et al., 2007). This educational approach enhances the connection between academic knowledge and practical application, preparing students for the complexities of modern industry.

Within the industrial environment, one of the key principles for continuous improvement is creating flow, as emphasized by Lean Thinking. This principle focuses on reducing delays, eliminating waste, and ensuring a smooth progression of materials and information throughout the production process. A crucial tool for implementing this principle is Value Stream Mapping (VSM), which provides a visual representation of the flow of materials and information and helps identify bottlenecks and inefficiencies. Studies developed at the University of Minho, such as Dinis-Carvalho et al. (2019), have shown how VSM can be applied in real industrial settings to identify waste and support Lean transformations and decision-making.

It was in this educational and methodological context that the present project was developed at SMSA – Indústria de Embalagens, as part of the academic curriculum of the Master's Degree in Industrial Engineering and Management at the University of Minho. The project integrated knowledge from key subjects such as

Process Modelling and Analysis, Advanced Organization of Production Systems, and Industrial Project Management.

The project was motivated by the identification of bottlenecks in the production flow of SMSA. Afterwards, a bottleneck was identified in the packaging area, where an excessive accumulation of inventory and prolonged queues led to substantial delays and frequent interruptions in palletizer operations. In response to this challenge, SMSA made a significant investment in a new packaging machine, aimed at standardizing the lines and improving production flow.

Therefore, the main goal of this project was to identify, address, and optimize inefficiencies in the production flow of SMSA, focusing on the packaging department where the bottleneck was identified, by projecting the benefits of the recent investment and exploring alternative supply scenarios through simulation. This simulation was built using real company data to provide an accurate and reliable basis for analysis and decision-making.

To ensure the effectiveness of the project, a structured PBL (Problem-Based Learning) approach was followed. The team held bi-weekly meetings, both in person and online, with company stakeholders and academic supervisors. Industrial project management tools were employed to guide the development process and monitor the project's progress in line with its objectives. Studies, such as the one by Carvalho et al. (2018), highlight the effectiveness of PBL in solving real industrial interdisciplinary problems and fostering cooperation between academia and industry.

Throughout the project, the team encountered several personal and academic challenges, which required resilience, adaptability, and a commitment to structured problem-solving. Despite these obstacles, the project produced relevant and applicable results, benefiting both the company and the student team. The integration of real-world data into a simulation model proved fundamental in supporting data-driven decisions that enhanced operational efficiency and financial performance.

In the following chapters, the challenges encountered, the methodologies applied, as well as the creation of various scenarios, in which determining factors such as the introduction of a new machine, varying the capacity in the rotation and the addition of a sensor in the mats were taken into account, will be analyzed in detail. The results achieved will also be explored, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the proposed solutions and their impact on SMSA's production system.

2 Project Development

The project was developed following a Project Based Learning (PBL) approach, whose purpose is for learning to occur through investigation and resolution of practical challenges, in a business context. At the University of Minho, the strategy is to encompass the course's various Curricular Units in a complex and challenging project, where students are encouraged to find viable solutions based on a real context, promoting more captivating and meaningful professional development. The project in question was carried out at Sebastião e Martins S.A. (SMSA), a medium-sized company in the corrugated cardboard sector, where the curricular units of Process Modelling and Analysis and Advanced Organization of Production Systems provided fundamental knowledge to fulfil the main objective, the improvement of the company's production flow. At the same time, studies were carried out in the area of ergonomics and human factors, which will not be the focus of this article.

With regard to Industrial Project Management, tools such as the RASCI matrix and MS Project were used to guide and monitor the development of the project, ensuring that it followed the initial planning and remained within the established deadlines.

The team was made up of nine members, supervised by two advisors, a teacher and a company representative, which involved consistent organization throughout the semester. Two weekly meetings were defined, one focused on planning and distributing tasks and the other dedicated to carrying them out, normally at the company's headquarters. In addition, several communication channels were used, including WhatsApp, Google Drive and Slack, aiming at informal contact, storing information and exchanging ideas and feedback with teachers and supervisors, respectively.

During the project development phase, the team faced several challenges, requiring adaptability and continuous effort from both parties. One of the main obstacles was coordination with the other curricular activities of the semester, given the size and demands of the project. At the same time, some difficulty was felt in defining the problem, given the scope of the proposed objective, followed by some lack of motivation on the part of the team in this initial phase. Finally, naturally, obstacles were encountered in the search for a solid and sustainable solution, namely in the collection, acquisition and interpretation of data.

Despite the difficulties experienced, significant results for the company were achieved, as well as personal/professional goals for the team members. The content taught throughout the Industrial Engineering and Management course was consolidated through the practical application of concepts, providing in-depth learning. Not only were technical skills developed, but also transversal skills were reinforced, such as teamwork, time management and decision-making based on real data.

The Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology structured the development and implementation of the project, establishing a strong connection between academic knowledge and industrial reality. Engagement with a real-world production challenge facilitated the development of technical skills in production flow analysis, simulation modelling, and lean principles. Simultaneously, the iterative and collaborative nature of PBL encouraged critical thinking, autonomy, adaptability, and informed decision-making, aligning with core pedagogical goals such as interdisciplinarity and reflective learning.

The final proposed solution was based on a simulation of the production system, where real data measured on the ground by the team was inserted. This simulation supported the proposal, demonstrating measurable improvements in both operational and financial KPIs, which is the project's major milestone.

3 Analysis of the production system - methodology

3.1 Bottleneck Identification

Analysing a company's production flow is essential to identify bottlenecks and optimize processes, increasing efficiency and ensuring the strategic use of available resources (Rogowska, 2018).

This chapter not only identifies the main bottleneck in SMSA's production system but also provides a comprehensive overview of the company's production flow. Understanding this overall structure is key to contextualizing where inefficiencies arise and how they affect the performance of the system as a whole.

In the SMSA production system, the process begins at the corrugating machine, where paper rolls are transformed into corrugated cardboard. This intermediate product is then directed to specialized machines that shape it into boxes or plates. Next, the product batches are transported by an automatic conveyor to the palletizing, strapping, and wrapping stages. SMSA's main final products are boxes and plates.

To gain a clear understanding of SMSA's production dynamics, the entire flow was directly observed over an extended period, enabling a detailed assessment of machine interactions and operational rhythms. Through this observation, it became evident that the buffer located before the palletizing stage was frequently operating

at full capacity. As a result, the automatic conveyor was often unable to collect new batches, forcing upstream production lines to stop. These interruptions led to significant productivity losses and operational inefficiencies, highlighting this area as the system's main bottleneck.

This constraint stems from the limited capacity of the system downstream of the palletizer, which processes all factory products, both boxes and plates. To further analyse and visualize this constraint, the production flow was simulated using SIMIO, a discrete-event simulation software widely used in manufacturing systems modelling (Sepúlveda et al., 2016). A picture illustrating this process is provided below.

Figure 1: Production flow after the palletizer

Figure 1 illustrates the system after the palletizing stage, highlighting the two processing sides: side 1, where most of the production flows, and side 2, dedicated exclusively to plates. Due to the specifications of strapping machine 2, plates can only be processed on side 2. The key machines involved, palletizer, strapping machines, and wrapping machine, are labelled for clarity.

Another critical issue identified was the low utilization of the strapping machine on side 2, which is dedicated exclusively to batches of plates. Since plates account for a small share of total production, this machine remains underutilized, while the strapping machines on side 1 frequently experience overload due to the high volume of box production. This imbalance further contributes to inefficiencies in the system after palletizing.

3.2 System after palletizer

The post-palletizing production system is a critical stage, as it determines the routing of products based on their type. For plates, the flow is relatively straightforward: after palletizing, they proceed to the first rotation and are directed to side 2.

On the other hand, boxes follow a different trajectory but still face constraints. All box batches are routed to side 1, where they undergo strapping. However, boxes are categorized into two types: with and without a turn. This classification depends on the pallet's orientation and the adjustments needed for proper alignment.

Turn-based boxes benefit from a more efficient flow, as they enter the first rotation in the correct position, allowing them to proceed directly to strapping machine 1 without requiring additional movement. In contrast, non-turn boxes require a longer process, they must enter the rotation, advance up to halfway, and complete a full turn to align the pallet before being transferred to the conveyor leading to strapping machine 1.

Additionally, between the palletizer and the first rotation, as well as between the first rotation and strapping machine 1, the conveyor belts are equipped with two sensors, allowing two pallets to occupy each section simultaneously. This strategic solution aims to optimize product flow, particularly during periods of high occupancy. If the subsequent operation (such as rotation or strapping) is in use, the sensors allow two batches

to temporarily wait on the conveyor belt before moving forward. This buffering mechanism helps minimize flow disruptions and provides greater operational flexibility, although it does not entirely eliminate the risk of blockages if the downstream resources experience excessive occupancy times.

The current system was modelled in SIMIO, allowing its comparison of the results obtained with the different scenarios created. Table 2 shows the values of the metrics analysed in a 24-hour time interval.

Table 1: KPI's results of the current scenario

	Current Scenario
Output	2053
Palletizer Block Rate	14.6%
1st Rotation Block Rate	2.6%

Overall, the current system configuration reflects a well-structured production logic, yet it faces significant challenges, particularly in optimizing trajectories and minimizing unproductive times. The design and integration of alternatives or improvements, such as the redistribution of trajectories or modifications to equipment, are crucial to enhancing overall efficiency and addressing the identified bottlenecks.

4 Study and comparison of different scenarios

Throughout the study, several scenarios were developed and analysed with the goal of optimizing the production system, ensuring the technical and operational feasibility of each proposal. These approaches aim to provide practical and effective solutions to the challenges identified within the production chain, promoting more efficient resource management and improving overall performance. Different configurations were explored to optimize the flow of materials, taking into account the existing limitations and opportunities within the factory. Given that the company is planning to install a new wrapping machine on side 2, this change was incorporated into the scenario development, allowing the boxes to be processed on both sides. However, the plates will only be routed to side 2 due to the specifications of the strapping machine, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the scenarios.

The first scenario proposes the use of only turn-based boxes, which are primarily directed to side 1 to make optimal use of the caterpillars. However, if side 1 reaches full capacity, the boxes can be diverted to side 2. This scenario is designed to maximize the utilization of the caterpillars, thereby enhancing the efficiency of the transport process.

The second scenario envisions the coexistence of "turn" boxes, non-"turn" boxes and plates. In this case, the plates are restricted to going exclusively to side 2, while the boxes, upon reaching the first rotation, can choose their destination, side 1 or side 2, based on rotation times and the availability of the subsequent machines. This approach provides greater flexibility in the system, allowing for dynamic decision-making to optimize the flow of materials.

In the third scenario, the inclusion of the ability to add corner protection in strapping machine 1 is considered. This change allows the plates, which were previously restricted to side 2, to also be processed on side 1. As a result, any product, upon reaching the first rotation, can choose the most suitable destination based on the availability of the subsequent machines.

In the fourth scenario, priority is given to passing non-"turn" boxes, which go directly forward at the first rotation, as the passage time is significantly shorter compared to directing them to side 1. However, if the direct

flow becomes congested, the boxes can be redirected to side 1. This approach aims to optimize flow efficiency while maintaining flexibility to manage potential bottlenecks.

Finally, the fifth scenario proposes the exclusivity of non-"turn" boxes, which preferentially go forward at the first rotation, using the most direct path to side 2 due to the lower complexity of transport. However, in cases of congestion on side 2, the boxes can be redirected to the opposite side.

In addition to these scenarios, the possibility of entering two batches simultaneously in the first rotation, provided they belong to the same order, was explored as a viable option. Furthermore, the study considered the installation of an additional sensor on the conveyor belts between rotations, as well as between the second rotation and strapping machine 2, and also the combination of these two elements.

These scenarios were analysed in detail, considering the impact of each configuration on the performance of the production system, particularly in terms of resource utilization. The best results of each scenario were achieved when the entry of two batches in the first rotation was combined with the installation of an additional sensor on the aforementioned belts, allowing them to accommodate two products simultaneously. Table 2 presents the optimal results of the different scenarios, enabling a detailed comparative analysis of the production system's performance under varying operating conditions.

Table 2. Scenarios

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5
Output	2239	2258	2265	2169	2175
Palletizer Block Rate	6.30%	6.17%	6.11%	9.56%	8.11%
1st Rotation Block Rate	1.85%	0.69%	0.74%	0.51%	1.56%

Table 2 highlights a clear performance advantage for scenarios 1, 2, and 3, all of which achieve output values above 2,200 units while maintaining palletizer block rates close to or below 6.3%. Among these, scenario 3 shows the best overall performance, with the highest output and lowest palletizer block rate, suggesting the effectiveness of equipment upgrades. Conversely, scenarios 4 and 5 display lower productivity and higher block rates, reflecting the limitations of less flexible routing strategies. However, it is important to consider the implications and requirements associated with each of these scenarios to make a comprehensive comparison. Scenario 1 requires an additional investment in pallet rotation mechanisms to ensure that all pallets enter the palletizer with the same orientation. On the other hand, Scenario 3 necessitates an upgrade to the strapping machine located on side 1, replacing it with a more advanced version equipped with corner placement functionality. This upgrade would allow the machine to strap both boxes and plates, enhancing flexibility in the production process.

In Scenario 2, a hypothetical situation was tested in which the buffer size after the palletizer was increased. The results showed that as the buffer capacity grew, there was a significant increase in the output of finished products, accompanied by a reduction in palletizer blockages. This trend underscores the importance of buffer capacity as a critical factor for system performance. However, the ideal buffer capacity was found to be 14 pallets, at which point the palletizer operates without blockages. Increasing buffer capacity beyond this would require considerable floor space, which may not be feasible or economically viable in practice.

The final decision on which scenario to implement should consider not only the efficiency gains but also the associated costs and the practical feasibility of its implementation in a manufacturing environment.

5 Proposed Solutions

Standing out for its adaptive approach, which allows products to decide their destination based on estimated processing times and the availability of subsequent machines, it is proposed that the current system be adapted to the one described in Scenario 2. The implementation of this scenario requires some strategic changes and operational adjustments that, although they involve initial investments, offer significant benefits in terms of efficiency and productivity.

The implementation of this proposal involves the following key changes:

- **New Wrapping Machine:** A new wrapping machine will be installed on side 2.
- **Additional Sensors:** New sensors will be installed on the conveyor belts, between rotations and between the second rotation and strapping machine 2. This change will allow products to move continuously to the next machines.
- **Adaptive Programming on the First Rotation:** The system will be programmed so that batches of boxes can make decisions about their destination based on the availability of the following machines.
- **Simultaneous Batch Entry:** The system must also allow for two batches to enter simultaneously in the first rotation, provided they belong to the same order. This measure aims to optimize production flow and reduce processing time for larger orders, avoiding the dispersion of batches across different points in the system.

These changes are expected to improve production efficiency by 10% and reduce palletizer lockout time by 57.7%, enabling more continuous equipment operation. Considering the company's annual turnover of approximately 50 million euros, the projected gains may reach 5 million euros annually.

6 Conclusion

This study at SMSA effectively addressed significant operational challenges by emphasizing bottleneck optimization in the packaging sector. Through systematic analysis and scenario simulations, the project generated actionable recommendations aimed at streamlining workflows, reducing lead times, and enhancing overall production efficiency. The proposed solutions underscored the importance of integrating real-world data into simulation models, fostering a robust, data-driven approach to process improvement.

A structured project management approach supported the planning, task allocation, and monitoring of progress, while digital communication tools enabled effective collaboration among all stakeholders. Managing the dual demands of academic and project work required adaptability and informed decision-making, contributing to the project's success.

The project highlighted the potential benefits of fully integrating the new packaging machine, emphasizing the necessity for timely installation and adaptation of production processes. In the future, the implementation of the proposed improvements and the continued application of scenario simulations will enable SMSA to transition to a more agile, sustainable, and competitive operating model.

Moreover, this case provides a valuable reference for both professionals seeking to optimise similar production systems and engineering educators aiming to incorporate real-world simulation into industry-based PBL initiatives.

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